

Advancing Human-Centric XR Interfaces and Situational Awareness in Industrial Machinery

Challenges and solutions:

Bridging the gap between concept design and real-world deployment required addressing multiple challenges. Ensuring intuitive, human-centric interaction in complex industrial environments was critical. Additionally, maintaining high levels of situational awareness—especially in dynamic, obstructed settings—and enabling effective remote operation posed safety and usability concerns. Translating user requirements into reliable, field-ready systems that maximise situational awareness was essential.

A user-centred design process was embedded from the start, involving operators in iterative XR prototyping and validation. This enabled early detection of usability and safety issues. Real-time people tracking, 360° video, and AR overlays were refined in lab and XR environments, ensuring seamless transition to machinery.

The system enhanced situational awareness by making occluded personnel visible and supporting decision-making with contextual AR cues. Field deployment required minimal adjustment, and remote operators quickly adopted the system due to its intuitive interface and safety-enhancing features.

Impact:

The XR-based, human-centric system significantly improved safety, efficiency, and remote operability in industrial environments. By combining real-time people tracking, intuitive AR guidance, and 360° situational awareness, it enabled remote operators to make faster, safer decisions. The system reduced blind spots, enhanced user confidence, and demonstrated how immersive design can accelerate innovation and ensure seamless deployment from virtual prototypes to real-world machinery.

Figure 1: From XR design to actual implementation in the reach stacker

KEY BENEFITS

Seamless transition from XR prototypes to field deployment

Enhanced situational awareness through 360° vision and AR

Intuitive, human-centric interface for on-site and remote users

